

Catchment Investment Decision Support System (CIDSS) input data derivation methods

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1 Overview

This document describes the methods and models used to derive data for input into the Catchment Investment Decision Support System (CIDSS), and includes:

- Delineating Planning Units (PU) and their physical and hydrological attributes within the Source Catchments,
- Identifying Microbial hazards within each PU and determining the risk to the quality of drinking water produced at specific Water Treatment Plants (WTP),
- Identifying sources of Total Suspended Solids (TSS) hazards within each PU and determining their risks to treatment operations and quality of drinking water produced at specific WTP,
- Identification of Intervention measures to reduce the risk to treatment operations and safety of drinking water produced at specific WTP posed by hazards or hazardous processes and
- Outlines ARC GIS models created within Model builder

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual workflow for deriving the CIDSS data and these are described in the following sections of the report.

2 Planning Units

Planning Units (PU's) are relatively homogenous areas within source catchments in which microbial and TSS hazards are identified and aggregated to assess their risk to the quality of water at their relevant WTP, and across which interventions to reduce the risk posed by hazards are optimised for effectiveness. PU's are hydrological units with area ranging from 1 to 9000 ha depending on channel network architecture (i.e., short distances between tributary junctions lead to small PU's) and catchment properties.

Large tributaries form the first level of catchment delineation at their junctions. Subsequent disaggregation (or aggregation) of subcatchments are based on geological boundaries, geomorphology, soil erosivity, density and type of past erosion processes, land tenure and land use. The purpose of deriving near-homogenous PU's in terms of the biophysical attributes and processes is to reduce the uncertainty in identifying and modelling hazards and hazardous processes within each PU, while the range of Intervention measures applied within each are reduced.

Some examples of factors used to delineate PU's include:

- Geology influences the geomorphology/landform, slopes, soil type, erosion processes, and the potential range of land use on a landform. Boundaries between underlying geologies coinciding with significant changes in the fore mentioned were used to further delineate subcatchments. Examples include boundaries between Tertiary basalt flows which have formed plateaus and where streams have incised into basalt and underlying less resistant geologies to produce steep gorges such as in Baroon catchment.
- Geomorphology or landform types of hillslopes, floodplains and streams. Stream reaches were delineated where significant changes in fluvial processes occurred. Fluvial processes may be influenced by underlying geology, origin of alluvium, slope, confinement and catchment area. Interaction between factors lead to different stream processes and form such as:
 - Single, meandering channel with a laterally accreting floodplain, or
 - Single, meandering channel with a vertically accreting floodplain with cut and fill history, or
 - Single, meandering channel with a vertically accreting floodplain with natural levee and avulsion history, or
 - Anabranching reach.
- Detailed soil modelling has been conducted in a number of catchments (Upper Brisbane, Stanley and Mid Brisbane) with Surface and Subsurface soil erosivity derived. Large areas of highly erosive (dispersive) soils were used to further demarcate subcatchments into PU's.
- Mapped gully erosion and landslides were used to demarcate PU's if significant differences in density or even presence/absence of these features were present.
- Large PU areas were maintained (or aggregated) under single tenure titles such as National Park and State Forest.
- Urban, peri-urban, and rural residential areas.

2.1 Source catchment – WTP intake Planning Unit Summaries

A total of 1445 PU's were delineated across Seqwater source water catchments supplying more than 30 current or future WTP intakes. Of this total, 1422 are terrestrial and 25 represent components of reservoirs and dams. Table 1 summarises the PU's contributing to each WTP intake.

Figure 1. Flow diagram summarising TSS and microbial hazards calculated for each PU

2.2 Physical characteristics of Planning Units

The PU shapefile contains attributes characterising its hydrological and sedimentological connectivity to WTPs, including the length of $\geq 3^{\text{rd}}$ order channel within each PU, the downstream connected channel distance from outlet point to WTPs excluding large reservoirs, dams and lakes. The disconnected distance represents the distance from PU outlet to nearest 3^{rd} order or larger channel and is used to apply a higher sediment deposition/decay rate. The connected downstream channel distances are separated into two channel types defined by flow regime as a surrogate for water travel time and is used to determine pathogen attenuation rates:

- High discharge: Daily flow exceeds $3 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for 70% of days per year, e.g. Mid Brisbane River (Fig.2A)
- Low discharge: Daily flow less than $3 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for 70% of days per year, e.g. All other intermittent and perennial streams (Fig.2B).

Figure 2. Daily flow duration curves used to define threshold between high and low flow channels

Dams along the flow path have the capacity to trap and attenuate sediment delivery to WTPs. Numerous factors influence the efficiency of sediment trapping including dam capacity, inflows velocity, inflow rate, stratification and temperature. Dam trapping efficiency therefore can vary significantly intra and interannually (Lewis et al., 2013). Due to limited monitoring data to quantify sediment trapping, empirical equations are often used to estimate trapping efficiency and numerous equations have been developed including Brune curve and Churchill curve which parameterise a constant and exponent to the ratio of inflow to dam capacity. Lewis et al. (2013) noted these equations overestimated trapping efficiency for Burdekin Falls Dam due to not considering the high hydrological variability of the subtropical systems. They proposed a daily weighting of inflows which produced good agreement with monitoring data.

For the purpose of the CIDSS, the trapping efficiency of TSS is required henceforth, the equation developed by Gill (1979) for colloidal and suspended sediment has been selected:

$$TE_a = \frac{\left(\frac{C}{I}\right)^3}{1.02655 \left(\frac{C}{I}\right)^3 + 0.02621 \left(\frac{C}{I}\right)^2 - 0.133 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{C}{I}\right) + 0.1 \times 10^{-5}}$$

Where subscript *a* represents the annual trap efficiency, *C* = dam capacity and *I* = inflow in the same units as capacity. A monthly weighting was applied to account for the hydrological variability by deriving the capacity to monthly inflow ratio:

$$R_m = \frac{C}{12I_m}$$

And substituting into Gill equation to get monthly Trap efficiency:

$$TE_m = \frac{TE_m^3}{1.02655R_m^3 + 0.02621R_m^2 - 0.000133R_m + 0.1 \times 10^{-5}}$$

And then summing to an annual Trap efficiency by

$$TE_a = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^{12} TE_m I_m}{\sum_{m=1}^{12} I_m}$$

Where subscript *m* represents an individual month. Monthly data for dam inflows from July 1890 to June 2011 were analysed and the median value selected to represent each dam as the monthly TE was not normally distributed. Analysis worksheets and results are in D18/162998.

Where WTPs are located within a dam tailwater (E.g., Landers Shute, Esk, Kilcoy), trapping efficiency is significantly less. Here, a volume to surface area relationship was used to estimate dam capacity to WTP and percent catchment area used to refine monthly inflows to recalculate trapping efficiency. Workings are presented in D18/162998.

For nested dams, cumulative trapping efficiency is calculated as:

$$TE_c = TE_1 + (1 - TE_1)TE_2$$

Where subscript *c* represents the cumulative TE, 1 represents the highest TE and 2 = the second dam's TE. The same principle is applied for additional dams. A summary of the TE results are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Summary of Planning Units for each WTP catchment, number of large dams and nested WTPs.

Basin	Catchment	Source	Supplies	PUID prefix	PU #	PU Mean Area (Ha)	PU area range	# Dam	Nested subcatchments	
Mary	Mary	Baroon Pocket Dam	Landers Shute WTP	Bar	102	64	1-291	1		
		Yabba Creek	Jimna WTP	Jim	10	762	93-3008	0		
		<i>Borumba Dam[§]</i>	<i>Mary River Supply Scheme</i>	<i>Bor</i>	47	832	58-2460	1	Jim	
		Mary River	Kenilworth WTP	Ken	66	990	6-5562	0	Bar,	
		Mary River Offtake	Noosa WTP	MRO	67	957	7-3488	0	Jim, Bor, Bar, Ken	
	Six Mile	Lake Macdonald	Noosa WTP	Mac	27	183	2-431	1		
North coast	Maroochy	<i>Cooloolabin Dam[§]</i>	<i>Image Flat WTP</i>	<i>Coo</i>	2	375	162-589	1		
		<i>Poona Dam Intake[§]</i>	<i>Image Flat WTP</i>	<i>Poo</i>	2	36	15-58	1		
		<i>South Maroochy River Weir[§]</i>	<i>Poona Dam</i>	<i>SMR</i>	11	260	2-496	0		
		Wappa Dam Offtake	Image Flat WTP	Wap	23	150	12-568	1	Coo, SMR, Poo	
	Mooloolah	Ewen Maddock Dam	Ewen Maddock WTP	Ewe	22	95	1-280	1		
	Pine Valley	Lake Kurwongbah	North Pine WTP	Kur	13	404	70-993	1		
		North Pine River	Dayboro WTP	Day	22	861	167-2886	0		
		North Pine Dam	North Pine WTP	NPD	22	721	159-1962	1	Day	
	Brisbane	Upper Brisbane	Upper Brisbane River	Linville	Lin	103	2019	19-7244	0	
			Wivenhoe Dam	Esk	Esk	154	2046	33-8067	3	Lin, Kil, Sta, Woo, Kir, Som
<i>Wivenhoe Dam[§]</i>			<i>Wivenhoe Recreation</i>	<i>Wiv</i>	17	2638	294-7836	1	Lin, Esk, Kil, Sta, Woo, Kir, Som	
Stanley		<i>Kilcoy Creek[§]</i>	<i>Kilcoy (Wade St) closed</i>	<i>Kil</i>	10	1293	77-2554	0		
		<i>Stanley River[§]</i>	<i>Woodford WTP closed</i>	<i>Woo</i>	44	566	7-3499	0		
		Somerset Dam	Kilcoy WTP	Sta	66	759	10-2835	1	Woo	
		<i>Somerset Dam[§]</i>	<i>Kirkleigh (Recreation) WTP</i>	<i>Kir</i>	33	1043	38-3450	1	Kil, Sta, Woo	
		Somerset Dam	Somerset Dam (Township) WTP	Som	9	1189	582-2158	1	Kil, Sta, Woo, Kir	
Lockyer		Lockyer Creek	Mid Brisbane River	Loc	195	1516	17-6093	0		
Mid Brisbane		Mid Brisbane River	Lowood WTP	Low	10	546	103-1150	0	Lin, Esk, Wiv, Kil, Woo, Sta, Kir, Som, Loc	

		Lake Manchester	Mid Brisbane River	Man	10	734	287-1345	1	
		Mid Brisbane River	Mount Crosby East/West Bank WTP	Cro	87	496	8-1625	0	Lin, Esk, Wiv, Kil, Woo, Sta, Kir, Som, Loc, Low, Man
	Warrill Valley	Moogerah Dam	Moogerah Dam WTP	Moo	20	1093	38-2295	1	
		Reynolds Creek	Boonah-Kalbar WTP	Rey	6	548	149-1045		Moo
	Lower Brisbane	<i>Enoggera Reserv[§]</i>	<i>Enoggera WTP</i>	<i>Eno</i>	2	1611	68-3155	1	
		<i>Gold Creek Res[§]</i>	<i>Future</i>	<i>Gol</i>	2	484	15-952	1	
Redlands		Leslie Harrison Dam	Capalaba WTP	Les	50	177	13-603	1	
Logan- Albert	Albert	Canungra Creek	Canungra WTP	Can	4	2297	784-4545	0	
	Logan	Maroon Dam	Maroon Dam WTP	Mrn	7	1463	395-2216	1	
		Logan River	Rathdowney WTP	Rat	18	2376	30-9069	0	Mar
		Logan River	Kooralbyn WTP	Koo	21	2388	304-6848	0	Mar, Rat
		Logan River	Beaudesert WTP	Bea	14	2500	220-5376	0	Mar, Rat, Koo
		Wyaralong Dam	Cedar Grove/Beaud.	Wya					
Cedar Grove Weir	Cedar Grove	CGW	33	1374	68-6307	0	Mar, Rat, Koo, Bea, Wya		
South coast	Nerang	Little Nerang Dam	Mudgeeraba WTP	LND	22	161	4-741	1	
		Hinze Dam	Mudgeeraba WTP	Mud	3	437	250-596	1	LND
		Hinze Dam	Molendinar WTP	Hin	32	510	51-1532	1	LND, Mud

§ Small WTP servicing recreation area or closed WTP which are not currently included in the CIDSS for optimisation, but PU's and codes still included for other WTP and/or for future use.

Table 2. Median dam Trapping Efficiency based on Gill (1979) using a monthly weighting and 122 years of monthly inflow data

Name	Catchment area (km ²)	Total capacity	TE median mnth wt	Alternative values*
Wivenhoe Dam	7020	3,245,238	0.968	
<i>Tailwater for Esk</i>		19,288	0.566	0.3
Somerset Dam	1340	980,849	0.954	
<i>Tailwater for Kilcoy</i>		9,410	0.520	0.3
Hinze Dam	207	310,730	0.954	
North Pine Dam	328	214,302	0.938	
Wyaralong Dam	463.6	102,883	0.952	
Moogerah Dam	228	83,765	0.949	
Baroon Pocket Dam	72	61,000	0.919	
<i>Tailwater for Landers Shute</i>		6,009	0.734	0.3
Borumba Dam	465	46,000	0.924	
Cressbrook Dam	320	81,842	0.966	
Perseverance Dam	110	30,140	0.962	
Maroon Dam	106	44,319	0.956	
Atkinson Dam	32.7	30,401	<i>n.d</i>	
Lake Manchester Dam	74	26,217	0.917	
Lake Clarendon Dam	3.4	24,276	<i>n.d</i>	
Ewen Maddock Dam	21	16,587	0.937	
Leslie Harrison Dam	87	13,206	0.797	
Kurwongbah/Sideling Creek Dam	53	8,590	0.866	
Cooloolabin Dam	8.1	8,167	0.929	
Lake Macdonald	49	8,018	0.819	

Bill Gunn Dam/Lake Dyer	3	6,947	<i>n.d</i>	
Little Nerang Dam	35.2	6,705	0.794	
Wappa Dam	69.7	4,694	0.643	
Poona Dam	0.8	655	<i>n.d</i>	

* Values used for when offtake located in a reservoir tailwater and water residency expected to be less than the proportional tailwater volume. N.d. indicates no data.

3 Microbial hazards

To identify microbial hazards within each PU and determine their risk to the quality of drinking water produced at specific WTPs, as well as the range of potential intervention measures that could be applied to reduce the risk, the method of Catchment Sanitary Survey (as per Baker et al. 2015) has been applied as an ArcGIS desktop analysis. In accordance with Baker et al. (2015), microbial hazards are considered in terms of the index organisms 'bacteria' and 'protozoa' to account for differences in concentrations in organism expected be generated from particular hazardous processes and differences in how these organisms behave and are treated at WTP. The index organism 'virus' is included in the assessment for Onsite systems, however currently the values for 'bacteria' are applied; future work aims to include 'virus' for each of the hazardous processes generating microbial pollution.

Hazardous Processes considered are

- Domestic Onsite wastewater systems (OSS)
- Sewerage Treatment Plants (STP)
- (Peri)urban storm water (SW)
- Intensive Livestock Agriculture and Industry (Ind)
- Broadscale (diffuse) Agriculture (Ag)

3.1 Onsite wastewater systems

Generally < 5% of OSS's have been physically surveyed in the Seqwater's routine Sanitary Surveys. Therefore, desktop assessment requiring use of Cadastre data and sewer pipeline data to derive potential OSS sites. There is little data available on the type of OSS therefore requiring assumptions on type until further data becomes available.

3.1.1 Methodology

Four main steps followed to derive the OSS input data:

Different datasets were used for spatial analysis to identify possible land parcels that were not connected to the sewerage network.

Land parcels identified were manually checked to look for existing buildings. A point was assigned to every presumed residential building.

Newly created points were analysed against other existing datasets and new attributes and scores were created.

Data upload to the CIDSS.

3.1.2 Tools

- ESRI's ArcGIS Arcmap model builder
- Python scripting within model builder

3.1.3 Data used for analysis

3.1.3.1 Spatial Data

Most of the data used came from Seqwater's local geodatabases, but some data had to be obtained from external sources. Three main types of spatial data was used:

3.1.3.1.1 Feature Classes

A copy of all the original feature classes was created and saved into the following geodatabase:
Z:\Working_Folders\SPP\CIDSS\Phase 4\Data\General.gdb

Here is a list of all the FCs used:

Sewerage:

- Seqwater stores sewerage line layers for most LGAs
 - o GCW_ERP_SEWER_PIPE_NON_PRESSURE
 - o GCW_ERP_SEWER_PIPE_PRESSURE
 - o LW_Sewerage_Pipes
 - o QUU_sGravityMain
 - o QUU_sPressureMain
 - o QUU_sService
 - o UW_sStoragePipe
 - o UW_sService
 - o UW_sPressureMain
 - o UW_sGravityMain
 - o RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_PRESSUREPIPES_P
 - o RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_NONPRESSUREPIPES_P
 - o RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_HOUSECONNECTIONS_P
- Missing sewerage data (Toowoomba and Gympie) was manually georeferenced and captured from their websites' public access data
 - o TOOWOOMBA_SEWERAGE_GeoRef
 - o GYMPIE_SEWERAGE_GeoRef

Cadastre:

- Seqwater geodatabases
 - o Lot_Parcels_20180319
 - o QAMF_Address_Point_20180319

Waterbodies:

- Seqwater geodatabases
 - o Water_Storage

Waterways:

- Griffith University was contracted to create a Channel Zone polygon layer
 - o Channelzone_for_Likelihoods

Geographical borders:

- Seqwater geodatabases
 - o Seqwater_Catchments
- Planning Units layer was created by Chris Thompson
 - o Seqwater_PU_v12

3.1.3.1.2 Shapefiles

Located in Z:\Working_Folders\SPP\CIDSS\Phase 4\Data\Shape Files

Here is a list of all shapefiles used:

OSS existing data

- Shapefiles of Baroon and Upper Brisbane catchments that were previously captured by Chris Thompson
 - o UBR_OSS_20092017.shp
 - o BaroonOS-31072017.shp

3.1.3.1.3 Rasters

Located in Z:\Working_Folders\SPP\CIDSS\Phase 4\Data\Raster

Here is a list of all rasters used:

Terrain

- DEM raster from Seqwater databases
 - o qld_gseq_z56.img
 - o CIDSS_Slope_Percentage_5m
- Soil composition rasters from Seqwater databases
 - o DSITI_Clay_0_5cm.tif
 - o DSITI_Clay_5_15cm.tif
 - o DSITI_Clay_15_30cm.tif
- Soil composition and Regolith depth raster from CSIRO website
 - o CLAY_000_005.tif
 - o CLAY_005_015.tif
 - o CLAY_015_030.tif
 - o REGOLITH_DEPTH.tif

3.1.3.2 Non-spatial data

Additionally to spatial datasets, [an older document containing metadata for the CIDSS](#) was used for formulas, conditions and assumptions. Here is an extract that is most relevant for the OSS:

Likelihood [*Like_score*] was calculated based Sanitary Survey methods (Table 4) which required the derivation of 3 factors and system function (*Tt_funcn*):

- Distance to Stream based on 50 & 100 m buffers applied to stream network taking into account channel width/size.
- [*Slope*] (percent) based on average grid cell slope from 30m grid where >10% = steep. Intersection used to identify on-site systems on steep slopes.
- Soil characteristics at the onsite system [*Soilrock*]. This information was derived from the DSITI modelled soils PSA and depth to bedrock based on values in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Characteristics of soil [*Soilrock*] at onsite system location used in determining Likelihood.

Soil category	Dataset	Characteristic
Sand	PSA - %Clay: 0-5cm;5-15cm;15-30cm	<10% Clay
Clay	PSA - %Clay: 0-5cm;5-15cm;15-30cm	>40% Clay
Loam-Clay loam	PSA - %Clay: 0-5cm;5-15cm;15-30cm	10 – 35% Clay
Rock	Depth to Bedrock	<30cm

- System functioning [*Tt_funcn*]. Due to lack of field data, all systems were (*most likely incorrectly*) assumed to be functioning normally.

Raw consequence for E.coli-type [*Ec_con_raw*] and Protozoa-type [*Pr_con_raw*] pathogens for Onsite systems assume 10 EP or less and were derived from Table 5 and represent the Logarithm base 10 of the pathogen load.

Mitigation measures [Mm_...] which reduce the raw consequence score are derived from Table 6. The attribute variable 0 = absent, 1 = present and is associated with a range of log reduction values (Table 6).

The pathogen consequence score [Ec_con_sc] & [Pr_con_sc] equal the raw consequence less mitigation measure, eg: [Ec_con_sc] = [Ec_con_raw] + ([Mm_...] + [Mm...] + ...) {note mitigation measure values shown as negative values in Table 5}

Table 4. Matrix of likelihood for contaminants entering waterways from on-site systems

Primary Hazard	Secondary Hazards	Buffer >100 m	Buffer 50-100 m	Buffer <50 m
Surface Effluent Irrigation	Hydraulic failure* Steep Slope**	Likely	Almost certain	Almost certain
	Hydraulic Failure* Moderate Slope or Flat	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
	Normal Function Steep Slope** Sand, Rock or Clay	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
	Normal Function Steep Slope** Loam or Clay/Loam	Possible	Possible	Likely
	Normal Function Moderate Slope or Flat Loam or Clay/Loam	Rare	Unlikely	Likely
	Normal Function Moderate Slope or Flat Sand, Rock or Clay	Unlikely	Possible	Likely
Sub-surface Effluent Irrigation	Hydraulic Failure*	Likely	Almost certain	Almost certain
	Normal Function	Rare	Unlikely	Likely
No effluent irrigation***	Hydraulic failure* Steep Slope**	Likely	Almost certain	Almost certain
	Hydraulic failure* Moderate Slope or Flat	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
	Normal Function	Rare	Unlikely	Possible

* Source: From Wivenhoe Sanitary Survey Report

Table 5. Raw consequences, all sewage systems*

Source	<i>E. coli</i> score	Protozoa score
On-site system (10 EP or less)	8	4
Decentralised system (~100 EP)	9	5
Small municipal STP (~1,000 EP)	10	6
Large municipal STP (~10,000 EP)	11	7

* Source: From Wivenhoe Sanitary Survey Report

Table 6. Mitigation measures, all sewage systems*

Mitigation measure	<i>E. coli</i> score	Protozoa score
Mm_Secondary = Secondary treatment	-2	-1
Mm_Chlorin = Chlorination	-3	0

Mm_UV = UV treatment	-2	-1
Mm_NoQ = No discharge (composting toilet, pump-out system)	-8	-5
Mm_Surf_ir = Land irrigation of effluent by sprinklers	-1	-1
Mm_Sub_ir = Land irrigation of effluent by sub-surface release (e.g. septic)	-2	-2
Mm_Buf50 = Buffer zone of 50 m or more in land irrigation area	-1	-1

* Source: From Wivenhoe Sanitary Survey Report

Modified Risk scores [Ec_{mr}] & [Pr_{mr}] account for the consequence and likelihood, eg:

$$[Ec_{mr}] = [Ec_{con_sc}] - (5 - [Like_score])$$

$$[Pr_{mr}] = [Pr_{con_sc}] - (5 - [Like_score])$$

The antilog of the modified risk score [$Ec_{tlog_{mr}}$] are calculated (eg, $10^{[Ec_{mr}]}$) which can then be summed within each Planning Unit by: $\text{Log}(10^{x1} + 10^{x2} + 10^{x3} \dots)$ where x = each sites modified risk score within a planning unit.

3.1.4 Data Outputs

Three OSS layers were produced at the end of this process. The first two layers were used to be uploaded to the CIDSS, whereas the third layer was just produced for reference, as it contains additional attributes that could be accessed if needed. The schema of all FCs can be found on this [XLS](#).

3.1.4.1 Upper Limits Interventions (polygon) - PU_OSS_ULI_%DATE_TODAY%

This layer has the planning unit polygons with the additional intervention score attributes. This is the FC schema:

Attribute Name	Data type	Description	Values
PUID	varchar2(6)	Planning unit unique ID	From the PU layer
ww_os_main	double	"Maintenance program" intervention score	The total number of OSS <100m from watercourse within a PU
ww_os_rect	double	"Rectify hydraulic failure" intervention score	50%(**) of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU (rounded to closest integer)
ww_os_upgr	double	"Upgrade systems" intervention score	30%(**) of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU (rounded to closest integer)
ww_os_conn	double	"Connection to mains" intervention score	OSS <50m from watercourse and \leq 1km from sewer network*

* This is just to see some numbers. Connection to mains requires a certain number (density) of very high to high risk OSS.

** They are both treated as totals instead of percentages at the moment.

3.1.4.2 OSS (point) - OSS_%DATE_TODAY%

This layer has one point per each potential OSS within the planning unit area. This is the FC schema:

Attribute Name	Data type	Description	Values
SITEID	varchar2(255)	Unique ID for on-site systems	Prefix "S" followed by 6 digits (prefix "LS" in the case of systems mapped before Stage 4)
PUID	varchar2(6)	Planning unit ID to which the OSS belongs to	From the PU layer
Like_score	Short	Likelihood score (likelihood of contaminants entering waterways from OSS)	Values between 1-5, where: 1 = Rare 2 = Unlikely 3 = Possible 4 = Likely 5 = Almost certain
Ec_mr	Short	E. coli modified risk score	Values between <0 - 7
Pr_mr	Short	Protozoa modified risk score	Values between <0 - 3
Vi_mr	Short	Virus modified risk score	Values between <0 - 7

3.1.4.3 OSS (point) with all Attributes - OSS_ALL_ATTR_%DATE_TODAY%

This layer is identical to the OSS point shown above, but has all the attributes that were not included for the CIDSS version.

This is the FC schema:

Attribute Name	Data type	Description	Values
DIST_TO_CHANNELZONE	double	distance from point to waterway	metres
LOT	varchar2(5)	cadastre lot	copied from cadastre layers
PLAN	varchar2(10)	cadastre plan	copied from cadastre layers
LOTPLAN	varchar2(15)	cadastre lotplan	copied from cadastre layers
STREET_NUMBER	varchar2(23)	cadastre street number	copied from cadastre layers
STREET_NAME	varchar2(50)	cadastre street name	copied from cadastre layers
STREET_TYPE	varchar2(50)	cadastre street type	copied from cadastre layers
CITY_PLACE	varchar2(82)	cadastre suburb & LGA	copied from cadastre layers
POSTCODE	varchar2(4)	cadastre postcode	copied from cadastre layers
ADDRESS	varchar2(300)	cadastre address	copied from cadastre layers
SITEID	varchar2(255)	parcel unique ID	value created in model to identify each parcel
OSS_type	varchar2(250)	Type of on-site system. Values brought forward from Chris Thompson's OSS old shapefile	-Septic tank -OSS with sewer connection -OSS
Mm_Surf_ir	short	Mitigation Measures: Land irrigation of effluent by sprinklers	"1" if mitigation measure present
Mm_Sub_ir	short	Mitigation Measures: Land irrigation of effluent by sub-surface release (e.g. septic)	"1" if mitigation measure present
Mm_NoQ	short	Mitigation Measures: No discharge (composting toilet, pump-out system)	"1" if mitigation measure present
Landus_cat	varchar2(50)	Landuse category	values brought forward from Chris Thompson's old shapefile
Catchment_Name	varchar2(255)	Catchment where the OSS is located	intersect from the seqwater catchment layer
REGOLITH_DEPTH	double	Depth to Bedrock	in metres
CLAY_PERCENTAGE	double	Percentage of clay in soil	0-100%
Slope	double	slope steepness	0-100%
PUID	varchar2(6)	planning unit unique ID	planning unit where the OSS is located
Soilrock	varchar2(20)	Soil category according to their clay %	- "Sand" if clay <10% -"Clay" if clay >40% -"Loam-clay loam" if clay is between 10-40% (*)
Buffer	varchar2(10)	type of buffer (from channelzone) the OSS fall into	- ">100m" if OSS was >100m from channelzone -"50-100" if OSS was between 50-100m from channelzone -"<50m" if OSS was <50m from channelzone
Ec_con_raw	double	Raw consequence score for E.coli	assumed value for OSS (10EP or less) is always 8
Pr_con_raw	double	Raw consequence score for Protozoa	assumed value for OSS (10EP or less) is always 4
Mm_Buf50	short	Mitigation Measures: Buffer zone of 50 m or more in land irrigation area	"1" if mitigation measure present
Mm_Secondary	short	Mitigation Measures: Secondary treatment	"1" if mitigation measure present
Mm_Chlorin	short	Mitigation Measures: Chlorination	"1" if mitigation measure present
Mm_UV	short	Mitigation Measures: UV treatment	"1" if mitigation measure present
Ec_con_sc	short	E. coli consequence score	[Ec_con_sc] = [Ec_con_raw] + ([Mm_...]) + [Mm...] + ..., where Mm = mitigation measures values (negative values, found in Chris Thompson's metadata document in Table 5)
Pr_con_sc	short	Protozoa consequence score	[Pr_con_sc] = [Pr_con_raw] + ([Mm_...]) + [Mm...] + ..., where Mm = mitigation measures values (negative values, found in Chris Thompson's metadata document in Table 5)

Like_score	short	Likelihood score (likelihood of contaminants entering waterways from OSS)	Values between 1-5, where: 1 = Rare 2 = Unlikely 3 = Possible 4 = Likely 5 = Almost certain
Ec_mr	short	E. coli modified risk score	Values between <0 - 7
Pr_mr	short	Protozoa modified risk score	Values between <0 - 3
Vi_mr	short	Virus modified risk score	Values between <0 - 7

(*) Originally from Chris Thompson's metadata document the "Loam-clay loam" value was determined if clay percentage was between 10-35. I changed it to 10-40 to close the gap (35-40) with no assigned value.

3.1.5 Model Metadata

All the OSS models used for this exercise have been stored in the following toolbox:
Z:\Working_Folders\SPP\CIDSS\Phase 4\Data\CIDSS-OSS.tbx
The models were named according to the order in which they should be run.

Step 0.1

Model name: **OSS_Step0_Clay_Join**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Joins a small raster to a large raster when they intersect, keeping the small raster data in the area where both overlap.

Input data:

- Large raster (floating point)
- Small raster (floating point)
- Seqwater_Catchments

Output data:

- Joint Raster (floating point)

Description:

The model was created to join two soil composition rasters (floating point) that intersected. One raster had more accurate data (smaller cells) but covered only a small area (3 catchments), whereas the larger raster covered all catchments, but its cells were much larger. The small raster was completely contained within the large raster. The model was designed to be used for any raster inputs of the same characteristics.

The process was:

- Reclassify large raster to cell size of small raster
- Clip small raster to the exact borders of the 3 catchments it included (to keep data consistency within each catchment)
- Join both rasters, keeping the pixel values of the small raster wherever both intersected

Step 0.2

Model name: **OSS_Step0_PU_Boundary**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Dissolves all planning unit polygons into one polygon (or multi-part polygon) feature class and creates three layers showing topography errors that need to be fixed manually.

Input data:

- Most up-to-date Planning Unit layer

Output data:

- %Name%_Boundary_TO_FIX_TOPOLOGY
- %Name%_point
- %Name%_line
- %Name%_poly

Description:

The model dissolves a multi-feature polygon layer into a unique-feature polygon layer, but the process requires additional steps due to problems with the layer's topography (gaps, slivers, overlaps).

The process was:

- Dissolve Planning Unit layer.
- Create a feature dataset with topology rules.
- In the new feature dataset create a point, line and polygon layers showing the topology errors. The names of the layers are linked to the input layer's name.
- Use the topology errors layers to manually fix the relevant errors in the dissolved layer.

Comments:

This process was preferred over a simpler one-tool geometry fix solution because of problems with the irregular boundary and large gaps formed by rivers.

Step 1.1

Model name: **OSS_Step1_Cadastre**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Creates a layer consisting of centroid points inside each cadastral parcel within the planning unit boundary

Input data:

- Lot_Parcels_20180319
- Seqwater_PU_v11_Boundary
- QAMF_Address_Point_20180319

Output data:

- CADASTRE_FINAL

Description:

This model uses the Lot_Parcels layer as the source for cadastral parcels and joins the QAMF point layer to add address information. Only parcels within the planning unit boundary are used.

The addition of address information is not needed for the CIDSS at the moment but was included as additional data in case it would be required in the future.

The process is:

- Clip the Lot_Parcel layer to the Planning Unit boundary
- Add the QAMF layer address information
- Use assumptions to delete irrelevant parcels

Assumptions:

- Adjacent parcels with the same LOT/PLAN value were dissolved into a unique parcel.
- Adjacent parcels with the same address values (street number, street name, street type) were dissolved into a unique parcel.

- Parcels are not included if their area is under 50 sqm or if their area to perimeter ratio is over 1.3.

Step 1.2

Model name: **OSS_Step1_Sewerage**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Merges all sewerage network layers available from each individual local government and utility in SEQ

Input data:

- GCW_ERP_SEWER_PIPE_NON_PRESSURE
- GCW_ERP_SEWER_PIPE_PRESSURE
- LW_Sewerage_Pipes
- QUU_sGravityMain
- QUU_sPressureMain
- QUU_sService
- UW_sStoragePipe
- UW_sService
- UW_sPressureMain
- UW_sGravityMain
- RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_PRESSUREPIPES_P
- RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_NONPRESSUREPIPES_P
- RW_CUL_UTI_SEW_HOUSECONNECTIONS_P
- TOOWOOMB_SEWERAGE_GeoRef
- GYMPIE_SEWERAGE_GeoRef

Output data:

- SEQ_SEWERAGE

Description:

Append tool was used to merge all layers into one.

Step 4

Model name: **OSS_Step4_Cleaning_Site_Data**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Creates a joint OSS point layer based on the manually shifted OSS point layer and older OSS shape files

Input data:

- UBR_OSS_20092017.shp
- BaroonOS-31072017.shp
- Seqwater_Catchments
- SITES_CENTROID_MANUAL_SHIFT
- Seqwater_PU_v11_Boundary

Output data:

- OSS_PU

Description:

The model joins 2 shapefiles with OSS data for Upper Brisbane and Baroon catchments to the manually shifted centroid OSS layer, creating a layer containing all OSS in the planning unit area.

The process consists of the following steps:

- Homogenise attributes of all 3 different layers
- Use catchment boundary layer to clear the 2 catchment areas from any possible overlap in the manually shifted centroid layer
- Append the 2 shapefiles to the OSS manually shifted layer
- Give the new OSS layer unique IDs

Step 5

Model name: **OSS_Step5_Generate_Scores**

NOTE: THIS MODEL CONTAINS VBA SCRIPTS. NEEDS TO BE CHANGED TO PYTHON

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Purpose:

Creates attributes required for the CIDSS and generates values for them.

Input data:

- OSS_PU
- REGOLITH_DEPTH.tif
- CLAY_5
- CLAY_15
- CLAY_30
- Channelzone_for_Likelihoods
- CIDSS_Slope_Percentage_5m
- Seqwater_PU_v13

Output data:

- OSS_FINAL

Description:

This model uses the data in the OSS layer's existing attributes, brought forward from all previous models and processes, to create new attributes that are needed to upload the data to the CIDSS.

The OSS metadata's criteria is detailed in [this document](#).

The spatial point data used from this step onwards will not be modified anymore (the number of points will stay the same and so will the location of every point).

Assumptions:

-Each clay raster was assigned a percentage value weight according to their depth (cm) (e.g. 15-30 cm clay = 0.5 weight of the total 100%)

Step 6

Model name: OSS_Step6_Upper_Limits

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Purpose:

Creates Upper Limit data for the CIDSS based on the OSS layer.

Input data:

- OSS_FINAL
- SEQ_SEWERAGE
- Seqwater_PU_v12

Output data:

- PU_OSS_ULI

Description:

The most up to date OSS layer is used to generate an Upper Limit table with attribute values for each planning unit.

A series of assumptions were made in order to assign values to each attribute.

Assumptions:

The following rules were followed to generate attribute values for every single Planning Unit

Intervention code	Intervention	Criteria
WW_OS_main	Maintenance program	The total number of OSS <100m from watercourse within a PU
WW_OS_rect	Rectify hydraulic failure	50% of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU
WW_OS_upgr	Upgrade systems	30% of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU
WW_OS_conn	Connection to mains	OSS <50m from watercourse and \leq 1km from sewer network*

* This is just to see some numbers. Connection to mains requires a certain number (density) of very high to high risk OSS.

Step 7

Model name: **OSS_Step7_Generate_Outputs**

Author: Walter Castillo (SPP)

Aim:

Generates output layers with today's date, based on the latest OSS layer.

Input data:

- OSS_FINAL
- PU_OSS_ULI

Output data:

- OSS_ALL_ATTR_%DATE_TODAY%
- OSS_%DATE_TODAY%
- PU_OSS_ULI_%DATE_TODAY%

Description:

The model uses the most up-to-date OSS data to generate the layers and tables that will be used to feed the CIDSS. There are two main steps in the process:

- Delete all irrelevant attributes for each layer/table.
- Include today's date as part of the outputs' naming convention. This intends to help keep track of every new data update.

3.1.6 Recommendations

- Seqwater's corporate geodatabases has data for most of the sewerage network available in SEQ, but there are some missing regional local government areas where data is not available. Discuss with the Spatial team about the possibility of acquiring these datasets to keep data consistency across the catchments. For this project specifically, Gympie and Toowoomba

LGAs were not available so manual mapping of relevant sewerage areas was done directly from data in their websites.

- All local governments and/or utilities should keep a record of On-site system facilities within their jurisdictions. Discuss the possibility of obtaining this data directly from them.
- Use sanitary surveys (delivered through Seqwater's Catchment Water Quality team) to improve the current OSS data.
- Incorporate data collected in projects delivered under the SPP Wastewater Key Program Area.

3.2 Stormwater

Stormwater locations have been taken from the Sanitary Survey data (G:\LWQ\3 Monitoring\1. Catchment Water Quality\3. Sanitary Surveys). Not all stormwater locations included in survey but, no additional data acquired as yet. Likelihood and Consequence score retrieved directly from Sanitary Survey Risk calculator spread sheet. In contrast to other pathogen sources, Storm water infrastructure contains different Treatments ([*Tt*...]) which determine the [*Like_score*] as presented in Table 7. Table 8 presents the categories for determining the consequence scores. Attribute field names and calculation methods as per Onsite systems above.

Table 7. Matrix of likelihood for contaminants entering waterways from stormwater sites*

Primary hazard	*Advanced SW treatment	Stormwater detention (ponds)	Pervious surfaces without formal drainage	Stormwater drains	Kerb and gutter
Stormwater	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain	Almost certain

* Source: From Wivenhoe Sanitary Survey Report

Table 8. Matrix of consequence for microbial hazards entering waterways from stormwater systems*

Hazards	Very small catchment (individual block)	Small catchment (city block or street)	Large catchment (multiple city blocks or streets)	Very large catchment (town or suburb)
No sewer system Failing on-site systems	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4	Major <i>E. coli</i> 8 Protozoa 5	Catastrophic <i>E. coli</i> 10 Protozoa 6	Catastrophic <i>E. coli</i> 12 Protozoa 7
No sewer system Well maintained on-site systems	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 4 Protozoa 3	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 5 Protozoa 3	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4	Major <i>E. coli</i> 8 Protozoa 5
Combined sewer / stormwater infrastructure High density urban	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 5 Protozoa 3	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4	Major <i>E. coli</i> 8 Protozoa 5	Catastrophic <i>E. coli</i> 10 Protozoa 6
Combined sewer / stormwater infrastructure Low density urban	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 4 Protozoa 3	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 5 Protozoa 3	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4	Major <i>E. coli</i> 8 Protozoa 5
Separate sewer / stormwater infrastructure High density urban	Insignificant <i>E. coli</i> 3 Protozoa 2	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 4 Protozoa 3	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4	Major <i>E. coli</i> 8 Protozoa 5
Separate sewer / stormwater infrastructure Low density urban	Insignificant <i>E. coli</i> 2 Protozoa 1	Insignificant <i>E. coli</i> 3 Protozoa 2	Minor <i>E. coli</i> 4 Protozoa 3	Moderate <i>E. coli</i> 6 Protozoa 4

* Source: From Wivenhoe Sanitary Survey Report

3.3 Intensive livestock and industry

Only a limited number of sites have been sampled under the Sanitary Survey program, therefore a desktop assessment is required using high resolution air photos and DEMs to Identify sites and calculate likelihood and consequence as outlined in the steps below.

1. Identify Intensive livestock and Industrial locations using the following sources:
 - Sanitary Survey data
 - ISA project's TSS point sources
 - High resolution air photos

2. Calculate Likelihood [Like_score] based on hazard category [*Hazard_cat*], pathogen source proximity/access to water course [*Buffer*] and [*Slope*] as categorised in Table 9 for Intensive Animals.

3. Raw consequence log values derived from Table 10. Herd size based on either estimate of paddock or shed size & number and/or livestock numbers present in airphoto as documented in the [*Comments*] field. Mitigation measures and corresponding field names provided in Table 11. Attribute values = 0 represent no mitigation, Value = 1 represents mitigation measure present and the log reduction value is provided in the Table. Remaining Field names and calculation methods same as previously described for the other shapefiles.

Table 9. Matrix of likelihood for contaminants entering waterways from agriculture*

Primary hazard	Secondary hazard	Fenced Water-course >100 m	Fenced Water-course 50-100 m	Fenced Buffered Water-course <50 m	Fenced Un-buffered Water-course <50 m	Direct Access to Waterway
*Intensive Animals	Steep Slope	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain	Almost certain
	Moderate or Flat Slope	Unlikely	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain
Broad scale Animals	Steep Slope	Unlikely	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Likely
	Moderate or Flat Slope	Rare	Unlikely	Unlikely	Possible	Likely
Biosolids	Steep Slope	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain	**
	Moderate or Flat Slope	Unlikely	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	**
Chemical & Pesticide use	Frequent / High Volume	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	Almost certain	**
	Infrequent / Low Volume	Rare	Unlikely	Possible	Likely	**

* Source: From Sanitary Survey Report

Table 10. Raw consequences applied intensive agricultural sites*

Source	<i>E. coli</i> score*	Protozoa score*
--------	-----------------------	-----------------

Deer (1 animal)	8	5
Cattle (1 animal)	8	5
Sheep (1 animal)	9	3
Pigs (1 animal)	9	3
Horses (1 animal)	7	2
Birds (1 animal)	7	5
Other (1 animal)	7	2
Small herd size (10 animals)	+1	+1
Medium herd size (100 animals)	+2	+2
Large herd size (1,000 animals)	+3	+3

* Source: From Sanitary Survey Report

Table 11. Mitigation measures, industrial and intensive agriculture sites*

Mitigation measure	<i>E. coli</i> score	Protozoa score
Mm_Secondary = Secondary treatment	-2	-1
Mm_Chlorin = Chlorination	-3	0
Mm_Lagoon = Lagoon treatment	-2	-1
Mm_VWetlnd = Vetiver grass wetland treatment	-2	-2
Mm_NoQ = No local release (hazard is physically removed from site)	-10	-5
Mm_Surf_ir = Land irrigation of effluent by sprinklers	-1	-1
Mm_Sub_ir = Land irrigation of effluent by sub-surface release	-2	-2
Mm_Vbuf10 = Paddock has a 10 m buffer zone with intact fencing	-1	-1
Mm_Buf50 = Grazed area is set back 50 m or more from waterway	-1	-1
Mm_Scatrem = Management practices to remove scats	-1	-1
Mm_Barn = Management practices where animals are housed in barns**	-2	-1

* Source: From Sanitary Survey Report. ** Only applied to Ag_diffuse.

3.4 Broadscale (diffuse) livestock agriculture

Limited Sanitary survey points for diffuse Agriculture pathogen sources have been collected. Therefore, a process to incorporate all diffuse agriculture (broadscale livestock) using spatial data was developed (Table 12). Landuse data (from QLUMP) was used to select Properties with Grazing native veg and Grazing modified pastures. The likelihood of diffuse sources of pathogens was evaluated based on property slope and livestock access/proximity to watercourse. Raw consequence scores are based on size of herd which was estimated based on dominant landform and grazing area of property (Lot&Plan). Currently, all livestock are assumed to be cattle.

The above workflow with processes and assumptions used for grazing parcel site assessment, existing mitigation measures, bacteria and protozoa risk and aggregation of values at a planning unit level has been achieved through a series of processing models which can be rerun to update underlying datasets or incorporate future subject matter assessments where applicable.

3.4.1 Grazing Parcels Schema

The initial stage of the model sets out to define the schema and domain values to be used when identifying grazing parcels, rather than building the schema as the model.

The preconditions for this feature class are a geodatabase containing an empty feature class and prepopulated domains.

Table 12. Field names and descriptions for the Broadscale livestock agriculture feature class.

Field	Alias	Domain	Description
PUID	PUID		Parent planning unit ID
Site_ID	Site ID		Concatenation of 'PUID' and 'DCDB_LotPlan'
DCDB_LotPlan	Lot/Plan		Lot on plan of grazing parcel from the Queensland Digital Cadastre Database (DCDB)
DCDB_Tenure	Tenure		Tenure from the DCDB
DCDB_Locality	Locality		Locality name from the DCDB
DCDB_Supply_Date	DCDB Supply Date		Date of data extract from the Queensland Digital Cadastre Database
QLUMP_Year	QLUMP Year		Queensland Land Use Mapping Program (QLUMP)
QLUMP_Primary	Primary Land Use		Primary land use classification
QLUMP_Secondary	Secondary Land Use		Secondary land use classification
QLUMP_Tertiary	Tertiary Land Use		Tertiary land use classification
Area_Ha	Area ha		Area in ha of grazing property, including adjacent planning units
Landform	Landform	Landform	Landform to inform livestock size
Steepness	Steepness	Steepness	Categorisation of slope across the majority of the parcel
Channel_Distance	Channel Distance	Channel Distance	Distance from the riparian channel/dam

Fenced50	Fenced	Fenced50	Fencing condition informing access to water
Source	Source	Int_Ag_Source	Animal type, to inform raw e-oli and protozoa risks
Livestock	Livestock		Stocking rate of parcel
Likelihood	Likelihood	Likelihood	Likelihood of e-coli/protozoa reaching the waterway
Mm_Buf50	50m Buffer	Boolean	Parcel set 50m back from waterway
Mm_Vbuf10	10m Vegetated Buffer	Boolean	Parcel contains 10m vegetated buffer
Ec_Con_raw	E-Coli Consequence Raw		Raw consequence of e-coli
Pr_Con_raw	Protozoa Consequence Raw		Raw consequence of protozoa
Ec_Mr	E-Coli Modified Risk		Modified risk from e-coli
Pr_mr	Protozoa Modified Risk		Modified risk from protozoa
Ec_tlog_r	E-Coli Transverse Log		Transverse log of e-coli modified risk
Pr_tlog_r	Protozoa Transverse Log		Transverse log of protozoa modified risk
Validated	Validated	Validated	Validation status of data

1. Schema description of grazing parcels

3.4.2 Grazing Parcel Identification

The identification of grazing land is based upon the assumption of accuracy of the QLUMP, which was conducted between 2012-2013 in South East Queensland, and 2009 in the Mary Valley, and the accuracy of the DCDB for its spatial boundaries. Across the majority of planning units the cadastral accuracy is +/-5-25m.

In order to identify cadastral parcels suitable for grazing, parcels for other land rights were excluded with the expression "NOT TENURE = 'Below the Depth Plans' AND NOT TENURE = 'Covenant' AND NOT TENURE = 'Lands Lease' AND NOT TENURE = 'Profit à Prendre'". Selected properties intersecting a planning unit were then dissolved on LotPlan, Tenure, Locality and Supply Date in order to consolidate a single geometry per unique LotPlan value.

From the current QLUMP datasets, land use matching the expression "secondary = 'Grazing modified pastures' OR secondary = 'Grazing native vegetation' OR secondary = 'Irrigated modified pastures' OR secondary = 'Livestock grazing'" was spatially joined to the selected cadastral parcels, keeping only matched parcels.

An additional field to capture the original area of the LotPlan in ha was created, in order to calculate stocking rates once the properties have been intersected with planning units.

An assumption on the presence of fencing was applied at a catchment scale and 'Fenced50' is included as an attribute of the planning unit, introduced as an attribute once the grazing parcels are intersected with the planning units.

All records greater than 1ha in size are appended to the defined grazing parcel schema, mapping to the fields refixed with “DCDB_” and “QLUMP” in addition to PUID and Fenced50 from the planning unit data. Three additional fields are also calculated

[Source]* = 1

[Site_ID] = [PUID] & "_" & [DCDB_LotPlan]

[Validated]** = 1

*Assumption that all grazing parcels are stocked with cattle until further assessment

**Desktop assessment- all values generated per this methodology

3.4.2.1 Grazing Parcel Outputs

- All cadastral base parcels identified as grazing through QLUMP methodology
- Original property area retained as ‘Area_ha’
- Transferral of Planning Unit attributes- PUID and Fenced50
- All parcels greater than 1ha appended to Grazing Parcel Schema

3.4.3 Distance To Channel Methodology

3.4.3.1 Watercourse Buffers

Innerchannels were derived from riparian channels identified through the ARI riparian vegetation analysis (Z:\Working_Folders\SPPVARI_LiDAR_analysis) combined with Seqwater’s dam fully supply levels. Due to the large geometries, the innerchannels were split by sub catchment in order free up enough system resources to perform the buffer analysis.

Multiple ring buffer (outside polygons only) for 50m and 100m ‘Distance’ intervals and a separate 10m buffer were generated around the innerchannels iterated through by sub catchment.

To remove overlaps between sub catchments all multiple ring buffers were merged into a single feature class. The Union tool was used to determine overlapping buffers and multipart features were converted to singlepart. All buffers within an innerchannel were erased. The remaining buffered areas were joined using a spatial join with a 1 to 1 relationship specified, and the merge rule for ‘Distance’ values was set as minimum. The resulting features were then converted to a separate feature class, retaining only the ‘Distance’ field.

To remove overlaps between sub catchments all 10m buffers were merged into a single feature class and then intersected with the planning unit geometry, then dissolved on PUID. In order to convert the buffer area to a polyline (to convert the buffer area to length for calculating mitigation measures) the Feature to Line tool was used. In order to retain only lines from the original buffer geometry all lines identical to the PU geometry were removed.

3.4.3.2 Distance To Channel

Channel Distance is controlled by a coded domain containing the values in Table 13.

Table 13. Distance to channel codes and buffer distance

Code	Description
0	100m+
50	0-50m
100	50-100m

All parcels that intersect the 50-100m buffer ring are assigned the value 100. A new selection is then made of properties intersecting the 0-50m ring buffer and are calculated as 50. Parcels where Channel Distance is “Null” are then calculated as 0.

3.4.3.3 Mm_Buf50

A mitigation measure is applied to a parcel if it contains a 50m fenced buffer of vegetation, represented by a Boolean domain of 0 and 1. By default all parcels are calculated as 0. Parcels that are greater than 100m away from a watercourse are considered to have this measure applied and are assigned the value of 1.

3.4.3.4 Grazing Parcel 50m Buffer

An intersection is performed on the grazing parcels and the 50m buffer and features are dissolved on Site_ID value. This is in order to identify the landform values adjacent to a watercourse.

3.4.3.5 Distance To Channel Outputs

- Distance to Channel field calculated
- Multiple ring buffer for 50m and 100m intervals around innerchannels
- 10m buffer around innerchannels
- Mm_Buf50 calculated as present if property greater than 100m away from channel
- Grazing_Parcel_50m_Buffer feature class retained as input for landform calculation

3.4.4 Slope Reclassification

Slope reclassification was required to derive (1) Steepness and (2) Landform. Here, steepness is used similar to Sanitary surveys to inform likelihood scores. Landform is used to estimate livestock carrying capacity of the grazing parcel.

In order to support the CIDSS modelling process a DEM mosaic has been produced from multiple DEM sources resampled to a 5m grid using a cubic resampling method. Where available LiDAR has been used, however gaps have been filled using 1sec STRM data.

The DEM has been converted to a 5m grid containing slope percentage values.

3.4.4.1 1.4.1 Steepness

Two classes of Steepness were assigned based on the average slope of the grazing parcel: Flats to moderate slope ($\leq 10\%$ Slope, New assigned value = 1) and Steep ($>10\%$ Slope, New assigned value = 2).

3.4.4.2 1.4.2 Landform

Four Landform categories are derived from slope classification, and then used to estimate livestock numbers for each grazing parcel (Table 14).

Table 14. Landform derived from slope categories is used to inform the livestock capacity of each parcel

Landform	Landform value in dbf	Landform definition	Stocking rate
Alluvial and Creek flats	Flats	Slopes $<3\%$ adjacent water course	2 ha/AE

Gentle slopes	Gentle	Slopes 3 – 10%	2.6/AE
Moderate slopes	Moderate	Slopes 10 – 20%	3.6/AE
Steep ridges	Steep	Slopes > 20%	10 ha/AE

In order to convert the slope into landform values, a landform domain was created, using the stocking rate (converted to an integer) as the code and the landform as the description (Table 15).

Table 15. Slope code and associated landform type

Code	Description
20	Flats
26	Gentle
36	Moderate
100	Steep

The slope raster is reclassified to the code values, although as 'Flats' can only be applied to properties adjacent to a watercourse, as an initial assessment 'Gentle' is classified as all values <10%:

Old values	New values
0 - 10	26
10 - 20	36
20 - 2500	100
NoData	NoData

'Flats' is reclassified a secondary raster:

Old values	New values
0 - 3	20
3 - 2500	100
NoData	NoData

3.4.4.3 Slope Reclassification Outputs

- CIDSS_Slope – 5m grid containing slope percentage value
- CIDSS_Steepness – 5m grid containing reclassified slope values
- CIDSS_Landform – 5m grid containing reclassified slope values for gentle to steep landform values
- CIDSS_Landform_Flats – 5m grid containing reclassified slope values for flats values

3.4.5 Grazing Steepness

Grazing parcel steepness is calculated using 'Zonal Statistics as Table', where the CIDSS_Steepness raster is the input value raster, the grazing parcels are the zonal data and the Site_ID is the zone field. The majority value is then calculated as grazing 'Steepness' for each parcel.

3.4.5.1 Grazing Steepness Outputs

- Steepness field value calculated

3.4.6 Grazing Landform

Grazing parcel landform is calculated in two stage. Initially the 'Zonal Statistics as Table', where the CIDSS_Landform raster is the input value raster, the grazing parcels are the zonal data and the Site_ID is the zone field. The majority value is then calculated as grazing 'Landform' for each parcel.

To identify grazing parcels adjacent to a watercourse where slope is <3%, Zonal Statistics as table is run on the CIDSS_Landform_Flats raster and Grazing_Parcel_50m_Buffer using Site_ID as the zone field. Where the majority value is '20' the parent grazing parcel is recalculated as '20'

****Note, this may need revisiting, particularly where parcels have flats near Creek and larger area of steep hillslope behind resulting in an overall class of steep and therefore small herd size when in fact large herd sizes are supported by small creek flat section of a parcel.**

3.4.6.1 Grazing Livestock

The livestock capacity of a parcel is calculated based upon property size and landform. The property size is taken to be the original parcel area ('Area_ha') to account for stock movement across planning units, and the stocking rate has been used as the code value in the landform domain. Therefore, the Livestock capacity of a parcel is calculated as:

$$[\text{Area_Ha}] / ([\text{Landform}]/10)$$

3.4.6.2 Grazing Landform Outputs

- Landform field value calculated
- Livestock field value calculated

3.4.7 Grazing Likelihood

The likelihood of contaminants from grazing reaching the waterways is calculated using the likelihood matrix, adopted from the sanitary survey methodology (Table 8).

The Likelihood score is expressed as an integer using the coded domain values in Table 16.

Table 16. Coded domain values for likelihood scores

Code	Description
1	Rare
2	Unlikely
3	Possible
4	Likely
5	Almost Certain

The calculations are based upon the Steepness, Distance to Channel and Fenced50 field values.

3.4.7.1 Grazing Likelihood Outputs

- Likelihood field values calculated

3.4.8 Grazing Consequence

The consequence of bacteria or protozoa is dependent upon source and herd size (Table 9). An assumption in the model of data is that the Source for each parcel is cattle. Herd size for grazing parcels is expressed as Livestock.

The base [Ecoli] and [Protozoa] scores are stored as a temporary join with an external table 'Source_Consequence' on the 'Source' field

E-coli and protozoa raw consequence are calculated as

1. if [Livestock] < 1
 - [Ec_con_raw] = 0
 - [Pr_con_raw] = 0
2. if [Livestock] <= 3
 - [Ec_con_raw] = [Ecoli]
 - [Pr_con_raw] = [Protozoa]
3. if [Livestock] > 3
 - [Ec_con_raw] = [Ecoli] + Log10[Livestock],
 - [Pr_con_raw] = [Protozoa] + Log10[Livestock]

3.4.8.1 Grazing Consequence Outputs

- Ec_Con_raw field value calculated
- Pr_Con_raw field value calculated

3.4.9 Vegetation Buffer

The vegetation datasets used to determine are the same used to calculate innerchannels for Distance to Channel. The data is split into 'geounits' where detailed classification of vegetation and geomorphology has been derived from LiDAR around major channels, and 'outside geounits', where vegetation within the riparian zone has been classified from either LiDAR, or where no LiDAR coverage exists, RGB aerial imagery.

3.4.9.1 Mm_Vbuf10

10m vegetation buffer (Mm_Vbuf10) indicates whether a parcel contains enough riparian vegetation in proximity to a waterway. This is a Boolean 0/1 value indicating absence/presence.

The default value is calculated as 0.

3.4.9.1.1 Outside Geounits

Insert text on derivation of outside geounit data

Outside of the geounit mapping the riparian condition is stored as an attribute of the mapped innerchannel. This is joined to intersecting grazing parcels through a spatial join. The spatial join fields are appended through a temporary join on 'Site ID'. Parcels selected on the expression are calculated as 'Vbuf10' = '1'

Grazing_Parcels_PU_Outside_Geounit.pct_5mPLUS >=30 OR
Grazing_Parcels_PU_Outside_Geounit.pctBetween >=40

3.4.9.1.2 Geounits

The riparian values within the geounits has been calculated solely from LiDAR and canopy height models, and the same riparian criteria has been applied to the geounit mapping. The geounit vectors have been converted to a raster 'Geounit_Pct5m' (identical raster processing environment to slope rasters) using the 'pct_5mPLUS' as the cell value.

The 'Water_Bufferzone_10m' feature class generated in section 3.4.3 is intersected with the grazing parcels to create a feature for each 10m grazing buffer area, including those outside a currently mapped geounit. This is then used as the feature zone for calculating a mean zonal statistic with the 'Geounit_Pct5m' raster. The zonal statistics table is joined back to the grazing parcels using a temporary join on 'Site ID'. Parcels selected on the expression are calculated as 'Vbuf10' = '1'

Grazing_Parcel_10m_Geounit_5m_Zonal_Stats.MEAN >=30

This may contradict analysis outside geounits, however greater weight is assigned to the geounit mapping.

3.4.9.2 Fenced50

The calculation of 'Vbuf10' can also be used to update the 'Fenced50' value

Where Fenced50 = 1 – Fenced and Vbuf10 = 1, then Fenced50 = 2

Where Fenced50 = 2 – Fenced and Vbuf10 = 0, then Fenced50 = 1

3.4.9.3 Vegetation Buffer Outputs

- Mm_Vbuf10 calculated by interpreting riparian vegetation classification
- Fenced50 value updated to reflect vegetation buffer

3.4.10 Grazing Modified Risk

The modified risk for bacteria is calculated from the raw consequence and the applied mitigating measures. Although not necessary as an input for the CIDSS as it replicated within the model processing, the transverse log of the grazing parcel risk is calculated in order to sum the grazing risk at a planning unit level.

3.4.10.1 Bacteria Modified Risk

The Boolean values recorded in 'Mm_Buf50' and 'Mm_Vbuf10' can be directly used in the model. E-coli modified risk 'Ec_mr' is calculated as:

$$([Ec_con_raw] - ([Mm_Buf50] + [Mm_Vbuf10])) - (5 - [Likelihood])$$

The transverse log of the e-coli modified risk 'Ec_tlog_r' is calculated in Python as:

```
math.exp( !Ec_mr! )
```

3.4.10.2 Protozoa Modified Risk

The Boolean values recorded in 'Mm_Buf50' and 'Mm_Vbuf10' can be directly used in the model. Protozoa modified risk 'Pr_mr' is calculated as:

$$([Pr_con_raw] - ([Mm_Buf50] + [Mm_Vbuf10])) - (5 - [Likelihood])$$

The transverse log of the protozoa modified risk 'Pr_tlog_r' is calculated in Python as:

```
math.exp( !Pr_mr! )
```

3.4.10.3 Grazing Modified Risk Outputs

- Ec_mr calculated

- Ec_tlog_r calculated
- Pr_mr calculated
- Pr_tlog_r calculated

3.4.11 Diffuse Agriculture Planning Unit Summary

To summarise the risk at a planning unit level the bacteria and protozoa values are aggregated against PUID. These values are converted back to a log10 score and appended to the planning unit table.

Summary Statistics tool is used to sum the values of Ec_tlog_r and Pr_tlog_r against each PUID value. Three additional fields are created in the table and calculated as:

Table 17. Field names, alias and function used to derive Planning Unit broadscale livestock risk

Field	Alias	Value
Ag_Diffuse_Ec_Con	Grazing E-coli	math.log10(!SUM_Ec_tlog_r!)
Ag_Diffuse_Pr_Con	Grazing Protozoa	math.log10(!SUM_Pr_tlog_r!)
Ag_Diffuse_Risk	Grazing Risk	[Ag_Diffuse_Pr_Con] + [Ag_Diffuse_Ec_Con]

4 Total suspended sediment

Total suspended sediment (TSS) hazard is derived from different methods for six hazardous processes:

- Channel erosion (Channel)
- Gully erosion (Gully)
- Landslides (Landslide)
- Point source sediments (PSS)
- Diffuse hillslope erosion (Hillslope)
- Unsealed roads (URoad)

Each of the hazardous processes had annual loads (t/y) calculated for each planning unit. Loads from diffuse hillslope erosion, channel erosion and point source erosion were derived as part of the Integrated Sediment Assessment (ISA) project (Ivezich et al., 2018; D18/138976). The ISA project also updated the mapping of Gullies. Details of methods of calculating TSS loads from these sources are detailed below else referred to in Ivezich et al., 2018; D18/138976. Unsealed road runoff and erosion is still being collated for inclusion.

As TSS is treated on a daily (or sub-daily) time step at WTP, annual loads were disaggregated to daily loads and converted to Turbidity (NTU) to determine risk at the specific WTP. Details of methods are described in section 4.6. Unsealed road runoff and erosion is still being collated for inclusion.

4.1 Channel erosion

The ISA (Ivezich et al., 2018; D18/138976) project developed a qualitative assessment of potential future erosion risk based on channel type, degree of erosion between 2009 – 2016 (LiDAR DoDs) and available fine sediment stores (i.e., inset units and bank geometry). Criteria used to establish potential erosion risk were also used to estimate a minimum and maximum channel erosion rate (i.e. t/y per reach or segment). Method assumes an annual average bank retreat rate based on a minimum and maximum channel erosion extent identified between 2009 and 2016 and applied along a percentage reach length depending on reach risk level. The estimate doesn't consider limits on available width, channel type, available adjustment mechanisms or that the erosion is episodic and related to large events. Therefore, the minimum erosion rate estimate is used for the CIDSS. The reaches are interested with PU's, then the erosion rate multiplied by reach length within each PU and summed to give total channel erosion load within each PU.

A comparison with focal catchment studies (Olley et al., 2010) showed that Normalising channel erosion to erosion per unit length, resulted in ~14 t/km for the Blackfellow Creek study while the ISA channel erosion based on a minimum rate predicts ~404 t/km, an order of magnitude higher. One reason for the higher estimate from the ISA project is because it is based on the 2009 to 2016 channel change which includes 2 (or more) extreme events leading to channel metamorphoses (change from a relatively narrow meandering gravel bed channel to a low sinuosity braided channel). Based on these data, ISA channel erosion derived from minimum rates are non-conservative and justify the application of the minimum rate over any higher rates. Further work to constrain the minimum rate is required, but no evidence exists that it is underpredicting channel erosion.

4.2 Point source sediments

Point sources of sediment from Intensive livestock (poultry, piggery, horse studs, feedlots) and other industries (quarries, construction sites) were identified as part of the ISA project (Ivezich et al., 2018; D18/138976). Initially a qualitative assessment, potential loads were based on bare earth area (or shed area for poultry and piggeries) with a unit TSS production rate of 31.2 t/ha/y. Extrapolated loads then grouped into 5 consequence categories. Likelihood of connection to stream is largely based on Sanitary Survey method depending on distance to stream, slope and number of waste capture dams present as depicted in Figure 3.

A potential load delivered to stream was calculated based on the delivery ratio as applied in the RUSLE diffuse hillslope erosion model whereby if point source is: <10m, 10-30m and > 30m from waterway, then the sediment delivery ratios applied are 100%, 35% and 10% respectively.

Figure 3. Flow diagram used to define point source sediment likelihood of connecting to waterway (\geq stream-order 3).

4.3 Gully erosion

Recent high-resolution air photo captures have highlighted the presence of previously missed gullies from Saxton et al (2012), as well as new gullies, headcutting and/or lateral expansion of old gullies. A new gully mapping exercise was conducted in zones of known higher density gullies. This resulted in an 20% increase in the gully network.

Existing gullies

The Sednet method was applied to the existing gully features mapped by Saxton et al. (2012) so as to take into account gully wall length for Erosion which has been shown to be a dominant sediment source within the gully complex (Wilkinson et al., 2015).

Table 18. Parameters for estimating gully erosion annual loads

Parameter	Field name	Description	Units	Data type
E	Erosion_av	Load of fine sediment eroded	t/y	Dependent variable
P	MergClSi	Proportion of <= 63 micron (Clay & Silt) from 15 – 30 cm depth	dimensionless	Continuous (modelled)
p	ASRIS_BD_1	Bulk density of subsoil from 15 – 30 cm depth	t/m ³	Continuous (modelled)
a	XSArea_med	XS area of gully where 10 th percentile ~ 10m ² , median ~ 40m ² , 90 th percentile ~ 90m ²	m ²	Constant of 40 applied
f	Prop_activ	proportion of gully length actively contributing sediment	dimensionless	Constant of 0.5
T	Age_T	Time since initiation which is derived from Saxton et al., 2002.	years	Discrete based on catchment
l	Length_m	length of polyline representing gully length	m	Continuous
SDR	SDR	Sediment delivery ratio	dimensionless	Discrete based on distance to stream/connectedness
Q_s	Sed_del	Load of sediment delivered to stream of 3 rd order or larger	t/y	Dependent variable

$$E = P.p.a f.l/T$$

Eqn.1

where parameters are described in Table 18. Parameters *a* & *f* contain the most uncertainty as they are actually continuous variables.

Parameters *P* and *p* were derived from two different scales of data; (1) DSITI soil model derived from high density of survey sites, and (2) ASRIS data based on low density soil survey sites. The DSITI data extent covered the Mid and Upper Brisbane and Stanley River catchments with remaining extent covered by the ASRIS data. The depth fraction of 15-30cm was used to represent the subsoil bulk density and percent < 63 um (Clay + Silt).

Not all eroded sediment derived from gully erosion is delivered to the Intermittent and perennial channel network (Stream order ≥ 3). Delivery of sediment depends on the gully (dis)connectivity to higher order channels. Significant loads can be deposited in the gully floor depending on energy gradients and across colluvial and alluvial surfaces if the gully is disconnected from channelized flow path. Therefore, a Sediment Delivery Ratio (Vigiak et al., 2012) is applied as a modifier to the Gully erosion load to obtain a potential average annual load delivered to the stream network (Eqn 2). SDR is based on gully spatial relationship to the stream network and stream orders/sizes as outlined in Table 19.

Table 19. Sediment delivery ratio applied to gullies

Spatial relationship to NRM WatercourseLines	SDR
Gullies mapped as WatercourseLine Stream order = 2	0.9
Gullies laterally connecting to Intermittent or Perennial streams (≥ 3 stream order)	0.9
Gullies mapped as WatercourseLine Stream order = 1	0.75
Gullies laterally connecting to WatercourseLine Stream order = 2	0.75
Gullies laterally connecting to WatercourseLine Stream order = 1	0.5
Gullies disconnected /No channelized flow path from bottom of gully to high stream order	0.1
Gullies mapped as WatercourseLines of stream order ≥ 3	0 (1)*

* These are considered under channel/bank erosion. However, Channel erosion calculations restricted to LiDAR extent and did not cover the majority of the mapped gullies. For this reason, these gullies are allocated a delivery ratio of 1.

$$Q_s = E \cdot SDR \quad \text{Eqn.2}$$

Data cleaning required:

- Some Gully polylines needed splitting because they are digitised down past confluences
- Sometimes two gullies were joined by node at their confluence and therefore needed splitting.
- There were also a number of duplicated gully features, each with unique ID's. This has likely occurred from merging of multiple data sets in the past. I am deleting the duplicated features.

New Gullies

Gullies not mapped by Saxton et al. (2012) because initiated since 2011, or missed in the original mapping exercise where identified and mapped across areas (5x7 km tiles) with high density of

existing gullies in a targeted exercise. These are referred to as 'New Gullies' and were classified into three categories: New, extension, re-incision for parametrisation of sediment load calculations as for the Saxton et al. (2012) Gullies (Table 20). New gully parameters are listed in Table 15. New gully age (T) is assumed as 5 years, unless already present prior to 2012 (i.e., Airphoto analysis indicates gully missed in initial mapping exercise).

New Gullies were mapped as polygons. Two methods used to derive gully length,

- (1) A minimum bounding circle around the gully polygon was computed, then the radius calculated with gully length estimated as 2 x radius.
- (2) DNRM WatercourseLines were clipped to polygon extent, Gully lines then summed within each gully polygon, then line length Joined to the Gully polygon shapefile.

Not all gullies intersected WatercourseLines and some gully polygons adjacent to streamlines resulted in only partial intersection. Therefore, a final gully length was assigned based on minimum bounding circle method were length of method (1) > (2) and were (2) was Null because no intersection, all other gully lengths were based on method (2).

Table 20. Parameter value changes for mapped New Gullies

SedNet parameter	Gully expansion	Gully re-incision	Gully new
Age (T)	5 years	5 years	Same as Saxton et al.
Proportion active (f)	1	1	0.75
XS area (a)	10	5	40

Focal catchment research from Knapp Creek (Olley et al., 2009; 2010) suggests fine sediment loads (t/y) delivered to stream are dominated by gully and channel erosion (Table22) and the sum of gully and channel loads from the focal catchment are similar to the sum of gully and channel erosion from the ISA project (Table21). The focal catchment study indicates a total gully length of 38 km giving a mean of ~ 150 t/km of gully erosion load. In comparison, the ISA project underestimated gully length with only 28km of gully mapped but predicted a slightly higher erosion yields of ~ 193 t/km of gully length. This suggests the gully erosion estimate for the CIDSS is not conservative, predicting a higher gully erosion load delivered to the stream network than modelled by Olley et al., 2009 & 2010. However, the data also shows the ISA gully mapping is incomplete with 10 km less gully length mapped, therefore underestimating the gully sources as expected.

4.4 Landslides

TSS contributed from landslides to the stream network was estimated following the methods used in Kemp et al. (2015) for Baroon Pocket Dam catchment (D15/122199, pp32-33). Here, the area of sediment contained within the mapped landslides was determined from an empirical relationship between landslide area and volume:

$$V_L = 0.074 A_L^{1.45}$$

where V_L is volume of the landslide (m^3) and A_L is area of the landslide (m^2). The delivery ratio of landslide sediment to the channel network was estimated as:

$$DEL = \frac{D - \Delta z}{D}$$

where DEL is delivery ratio of a landslide sediment to the stream network, D is runout distance, and Δz is distance between the centroid of the landslide area and the nearest downslope stream channel or lake. If $D < \Delta z$, then DEL is set to zero. Runout distance (D) is calculated as

$$D = 25V_L^{0.3}$$

where V_L is volume of the landslide (m^3) and Δz is calculated within ArcGIS. The volume of landslide derived fine sediment delivered to the stream network (Q_{LS}) is:

$$Q_{LS} = \frac{V_L \times DEL \times \rho \times P}{T} \times t \times V_r$$

where ρ is sediment bulk density (1.2 tm^{-3}), P is the proportion of fine sediment (0.5), T is time since initial landslide (assumed 80 years after Kemp et al., 2015), t is the temporal reduction factor (0.3), and V_r is the reduction due to (re)vegetation resistance which is 0.1 for high cover of woody vegetation else 1.

4.5 Diffuse hillslope erosion

4.5.1 Current method

Diffuse hillslope erosion prediction is based on RUSLE modelled load on a 5m grid. Factors K, L, S, E and C were provided by Alluvium as part of ISA project (Ivezich et al., 2018; D18/138976). C-factors were QA'd and updated as follows:

- (1) Natural rock/cliff C-factor was originally set to 0.5 as per bare earth. This resulted in many of the mountainous peaks (e.g. Mt Barney, Mt Maroon, etc.) having the highest TSS loads. Natural rock and cliff was set to 0.001
- (2) Used data from AussieGrass (DSITI, 2015) to determine pasture grass cover and apply function of Silburn (2011) to convert percent cover to C-factor to produce a spatially (LGA) variable grass cover factor (Table21)
- (3) Applied C-factors for cropping as defined by Blackley et al.(2015) and Silburn (2011)
- (4) Dryland cropping landcover incorrectly mapped. For example, in Logan catchment > 90% of attributed grid cells to dryland cropping was actually farm dams. Dams applied C-factor for Water.
- (5) 255 polygons mapped as cloud and allocated a C-factor of 0.2. Used 2015 airphoto to identify landcover and derive a C-factor for the largest polygons

Additionally, Channel zones, point sources, and landslides were masked and removed from diffuse hillslope calculations to avoid double counting. The Riparian zones from ARI LiDAR analysis project were used as a mask to encapsulate the channel banks/channel zones.

The Index of Connectivity method of Borselli et al. (2008) which is conceptually superior method of determining SDR using a sediment delivery/ sediment retention model was applied. The Borselli et al. (2008) method has been coded into the InVEST Sediment Delivery model which was used to model sediment loads delivered to watercourses with RUSLE and SDR based on Index of Connectivity (Hamel et al., 2015).

The InVEST sediment delivery module is a spatially-explicit model working at the spatial resolution of the input digital elevation model (DEM) raster. For each pixel, the model first computes the amount of annual soil loss from that pixel, then computes the sediment delivery ratio (SDR), which is the proportion of soil loss actually reaching the catchment outlet. This approach was proposed by Borselli et al. (2008) and has received increasing interest in recent years (Cavalli et al., 2013; López-vicente et al., 2013; Sougnez et al., 2011).

The SDR is based on the work by Borselli et al. (2008), the model first computes the connectivity index (IC) for each pixel. The connectivity index describes the hydrological linkage between sources of sediment (from the landscape) and sinks (like streams.) Higher values of IC indicate that source erosion is more likely to make it to a sink (i.e. is more connected), which happens, for example, when there is sparse vegetation or higher slope. Lower values of IC (i.e. lower connectivity) are associated with more vegetated areas and lower slopes.

IC is a function of both the area upslope of each pixel (D_{up}) and the flow path between the pixel and the nearest stream (D_{dn}). If the upslope area is large, has lower slope, and good vegetative cover (so a low USLE C factor), D_{up} will be low, indicating a lower potential for sediment to make it to the stream. Similarly, if the downslope path between the pixel and the stream is long, has lower slope and good vegetative cover, D_{dn} will be low.

IC is calculated as follows:

$$IC = \log_{10}(D_{up}/D_{dn})$$

Figure 4. Conceptual approach used in the model (Borselli et al. 2018). The sediment delivery ratio (SDR) for each pixel is a function of the upslope area and downslope flow path (source <http://data.naturalcapitalproject.org/nightly-build/invest-users-guide/html/sdr.html>)

D_{up} is the upslope component defined as:

$$D_{up} = CS\sqrt{A}$$

where C is the average C factor of the upslope contributing area, S is the average slope gradient of the upslope contributing area (m/m) and A is the upslope contributing area (m^2). The upslope contributing area is delineated from the D-infinity flow algorithm (Tarboton, 1997).

The downslope component D_{dn} is given by:

$$D_{dn} = \sum \frac{d_i}{C_i S_i}$$

where d_i is the length of the flow path along the i th cell according to the steepest downslope direction (m) (see Figure 4), C_i and S_i are the C factor and the slope gradient of the i th cell, respectively. Again, the downslope flow path is determined from the D-infinity flow algorithm (Tarboton, 1997).

To avoid infinite values for IC , slope values S are forced to a minimum of 0.005 m/mm/m if they occur to be less than this threshold, and an upper limit of 1 m/m to limit bias due to very high values of IC on steep slopes. (Cavalli et al., 2013).

The SDR ratio for a pixel i is then derived from the conductivity index IC following (Vigiak et al., 2012):

$$SDR_i = SDR_{max} / (1 + \exp((IC_0 - IC_i)/k))$$

where SDR_{max} is the maximum theoretical SDR, set to an average value of 0.8 (Vigiak et al., 2012), and IC_0 and k are calibration parameters that define the shape of the SDR- IC relationship (which is an increasing function).

The effect of the calibration are illustrated by setting $k_b=1$ and $k_b=2$ (solid and dashed line, respectively), and $IC_0=0.5$ and $IC_0=2$ (black and grey dashed lines, respectively).

The sediment load (or export, as it is called in the model results) from a given pixel i E_i (units: $tons \cdot ha^{-1} \cdot yr^{-1}$), is the amount of sediment eroded from that pixel that actually reaches the stream. Sediment export is given by:

$$E_i = usle_i \cdot SDR_i$$

The Sediment delivery model InVEST 3.5 was configured and run:

- The (sub)catchment scale due to computer processing limitations
- 5m grid cell size
- Using a merged dam and channel bed grid (from Geounit mapping) as a channel mask
- Used ISA project R and K -factors and the updated C-factor
- Threshold flow accumulation applied is 4000 (10 ha)
- The maximum SDR, $SDR_{max} = 0.8$
- The calibration parameters k_b and IC_o were set to 1 and 0.5 respectively

To determine diffuse hillslope eroded sediment delivered to the stream network for each PU, the data was converted to tons per grid cell (divided by 400), then summed using Zonal Statistics based on PUID codes for each Planning Unit. Based on these InVEST model settings, significantly reduced diffuse hillslope sediment loads were predicted compared with using simple distance classes for SDR (see Appendix 1). However, these loads are still a large source in most Planning Units and ongoing refinement or improvement is necessary. It is noted that Waters et al. (2014) used a range of models to predict TSS yields across the whole of the Great Barrier Reef (GBR) based on a daily timestep (Table 22). Of note, HowLeaky was the preferred model for cropping land use instead of RUSLE. The application of HowLeaky as a model to predict TSS loads from cropping/horticulture areas across SEQLD catchments should be investigated further.

Table 21. Land use code and C-factor values applied in RUSLE

Code	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	Landcover	Land use (matched)	C factor by Alluvium	C factor updated
1	B Non-vegetated areas	B1 Terrestrial non-vegetated	B15 Built-up and associated area	Impervious Road Surface	Barren land (construction)	0.5	0.5
2	NA	NA	NA	Cloud	NA	0.2	Used airphotos to interpret underlying LU
3	B Non-vegetated areas	B2 Aquatic non-vegetated	B28 Inland or marine water	Ocean	Water	0	0
5	B Non-vegetated areas	B1 Terrestrial non-vegetated	B15 Built-up and associated area	Mine Quarry Industrial	Barren land (construction)	0.5	0.5
6	B Non-vegetated areas	B2 Aquatic non-vegetated	B28 Inland or marine water	Waterbody	Water	0	0
8	B Non-vegetated areas	B2 Aquatic non-vegetated	B27 Artificial water bodies	Canal	Water	0	0
9	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A12 Natural and semi vegetation	Native Forest	Forest (vegetated)	0.004	0.004
10	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A11 Cultivated terrestrial	Plantation	Forest (vegetated)	0.004	0.004
11	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A12 Natural and semi vegetation	Non-forest Native Vegetation	Forest (vegetated)	0.004	0.004
13	B Non-vegetated areas	B1 Terrestrial non-vegetated	B18 Bare areas	Sand Mud Bank	Barren land (construction)	0.5	0.5
14_	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A11 Cultivated terrestrial	Grass	Dry land pasture/shrub land (agriculture)	0.05	Upper Brisbane 0.013 [Code = 1413] Stanley 0.011 [Code = 1411] Lockyer 0.009 [Code = 1409] Mid Brisbane 0.009 Upper Mary 0.013 Small coastal 0.010 [Code = 1410] Logan 0.014 [Code = 1414] Nerang 0.010

15	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A11 Cultivated terrestrial	Tree Crop	Forest (vegetated)	0.004	0.004
16	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A11 Cultivated terrestrial	Irrigated Crop and Pasture	Irrigated Pasture	0.125	0.15
17	A Vegetated	A1 Vegetated terrestrial	A11 Cultivated terrestrial	Dryland Crop	Dry land pasture/shrub land (agriculture)	0.05	0.125
18	B Non-vegetated areas	B1 Terrestrial non-vegetated	B18 Bare areas	Natural Rock Cliff	Barren land (construction)	0.5	0.001
19	B Non-vegetated areas	B1 Terrestrial non-vegetated	B15 Built-up and associated area	Non-vegetated	Settlement (urban)	0.002	0.002
20	B Non-vegetated areas	B2 Aquatic non-vegetated	B27 Artificial water bodies	Farm dams	Water	n/a	0

Code 14 values derived using AussieGrass [<https://www.longpaddock.qld.gov.au/aussiegrass>] model and conversion equations of Silburn, 2011. Worksheets saved in D20/0191844.

C-Factor = $\text{Exp}(a + b.\text{cover}\% + c.\text{cover}\% + d.\text{cover}\%)$ where cover% = last 5y average of Local Government Area pasture total cover (%), a = -0.7986, b = -0.47384, c = 0.0004488, d = -5.2035E-6.

Table 22. Models used in Waters et al. (2014) for all GBR modelling of TSS yield

Land use:	Sugarcane	Cropping	Grazing
Model:	APSIM	HowLeaky	RUSLE

4.6 Disaggregation of TSS annual load to TSS risk thresholds at WTP

TSS risk at WTP is based on thresholds for turbidity, measured in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU), that when exceeded require an operational response at a WTP to ensure drinking water is produced to an acceptable quality; i.e. a criterion that separates acceptability from unacceptability. Hence, an instantaneous NTU threshold value is converted to TSS Annual load threshold based on a disaggregation of TSS annual load into daily loads derived from Q-TSS relationship and conversion from TSS to NTU based empirical relationships derived from Queensland-wide data (*ref from Marsh*). This method is described in the following steps which are contained within excel worksheets embedded with empirical equations and other formulae. The NTU risk level thresholds applied to each WTP (RaP – risk at plant) are in *D18/106090*.

The following steps are applied to determine TSS risk at WTP thresholds:

1. Download discharge data (ML/day) from nearest gauging station with a minimum of 10 years record (Table 28)
2. Calculate Raw TSS (mg/L) from Daily discharge record as:

$$TSS_{raw} = 0.0743 + 0.0043 \times \frac{Q}{Q_{10}} \times TSS_{max} \text{ if no zero intercept, else}$$

$$TSS_{raw} = 0.005671 \times \frac{Q}{Q_{10}} \times TSS_{max} \text{ if zero intercept,}$$

Where TSS_{max} is known upper limit concentration of TSS (mg/L), Q₁₀ is the 90th percentile value of the discharge record

3. Rescale based on known annual load
4. Calculate daily NTU as:

$$NTU = \left(\frac{TSS_{rescaled}}{4.19} \right)^{1.8975} \text{ if } Q < Q_{10}$$

$$NTU = \left(\frac{TSS_{rescaled}}{2.49} \right)^{1.267} \text{ if } Q > Q_{10}$$

5. Calculate acceptable NTU based on Risk at Plant (RaP) NTU thresholds
 - a. If Calculated NTU is < Catastrophic risk threshold, then NTU = original value, otherwise = Catastrophic threshold value
 - b. If Calculated NTU is < Major risk threshold, then NTU = original value, otherwise = Major threshold value
 - c. Repeat for Moderate, Minor and Insignificant
6. Calculate acceptable TSS in kg/day based on Risk at Plant (RaP) NTU thresholds
 - a. If Calculated NTU is < catastrophic threshold value, then
 - i. **Acceptable.TSS** = $\frac{Q \times TSS_{raw}}{1000000}$ else
 - ii. **Acceptable.TSS** = **Acceptable.NTU**^{-1.267} × 2.49 × Q
 - b. Repeat for Major, Moderate, Minor and Insignificant.
7. Calculate threshold TSS annual load (t/y) as:
 - a. Catastrophic: Average value of Catastrophic Acceptable
TSS x 365.25 / 1000
 - b. Repeat for Major, Moderate, Minor and Insignificant.

Table 23. Discharge data used to disaggregate TSS loads at receiving WTPs*

Intake/WTP	Code	GS name	GS #	Record period (Cal.y / y)	Comments
Linville	TLI	Brisbane R @ Linville	143007A	1964-2018 / 54	
Esk	TES	Brisbane R @ Gregors Ck	143009A	1962-2018 / 56	
Kilcoy	TKY	Stanely R @ Woodford	143901A	2002-2018 / 16	
Somerset	TST	Stanely R @ Woodford	143901A	2002-2018 / 16	
Lockyer	CLV	O'Reilly's Weir	143207A	1948-2015 / 67	
Lowood	TLO	Savages Xing	143001C	1958-2018 / 60	
Mt Crosby East	TEB	Savages Xing	143001C	1958-2018 / 60	
Mt Crosby West	TWB	Savages Xing	143001C	1958-2018 / 60	
Jimna	TJI	Yabba Ck @ Imbil	138105CD	1929-1982 / 53	
Baroon/Landers	TLS	Obi Obi @ Gardners Falls		1986-2017 / 31	
Kenilworth	TKE	Mary R @ Moy Pocket	138111A	1963-2018 / 55	
Mary R Offtake	MRO	Mary R @ Fishermans Pocket	138007A	1968-2018 / 50	
Lake MacDonald	LMD	Six Mile Ck @ Cooran	138107B	1981-2018 / 27	Downstream of Dam
Noosa WTP	TNO	Fishermans Pocket	138007A	1968-2018 / 50	For combined MRO & LMD TSS risk
Wappa Dam	TIF	South Maroochy @ Kiamba	141001B	1985-2018 / 33	Combined all intakes for Image Flat because all intakes relatively close and dependent
Ewen Maddock	TEM	Mooloolah R @ Mooloolah	141006A	1971-2018 / 47	Adjacent subcatchment to Ewen
Dayboro Wells	TDY	North Pine R @ Dayboro	142106A	1998-2009 / 11	
North Pine Dam	TNP	North Pine @ Youngs X	142101A	1915-1978 / 63	Closed station, measuring pre-dam

Moogerah Dam	TMG	Reynolds Ck @ Moogerah Tailwater	145112A	1980-2002 / 22	
Boonah-Kalbar	TBK	Reynolds Ck @ Moogerah	143103AB	1917-1960 / 43	Closed GS at ~ site of dam wall
Maroon Dam	TMD	Burnett Ck @ Upstream Maroon Dam	145018A	1970-2018 / 48	Upstream of dam tailwater
Rathdowny	TRA	Logan R @ Rathdowney	145020A	1973-2018 / 45	
Kooralbyn	TKO	Logan R @ Bromelton Weir	145025A	1997-2011 / 4	GS downstream from intake. Maybe use Rathdowny
Beaudesert	TBE	Logan R @ Round Mtn	145008A	1964-2018 / 54	Downstream of WTP
Wyaralong Dam	TWY	Teviot Ck @ Coulson	145031A	2011-2018 / 7	*To be pumped to CGW or Beaudesert pipeline in future
Cedar Grove	CGW	Logan R @ Yarrahappini	145014A	1969-2018 / 49	Downstream of weir
Canungra WTP	TCN	Canungra Ck @ Main Road Bridge	145107A	1973-2018 / 45	Downstream from Canungra town
Little Nerang Dam for TMU	LND	Little Nerang R	142007A & 142009A	1926-1974 / 48	Closed stations pre-dam, use for both intakes
Hinze Dam for TMU	TMU	Little Nerang R	142007A & 142009A	1926-1974 / 48	As above
Hinze Dam for TMO	TMO	Nerang R @ Numinbah	146015A	2007-2018 / 11	
Leslie Harrison/ Capalaba WTP	TCP	No Q found yet			

*Small recreation WTP from Wivenhoe, Kirkleigh, Borumba and closed WTP of Petrie (Lake Kurwongaba), Kilcoy (Wade St) and Enoggera are not currently used in the CIDSS.

5 Intervention Upper Limits

Methods and assumptions applied to calculate the upper limits for each intervention within a Planning Unit are described below.

5.1 TSS Intervention Upper Limits

5.1.1 River channel stabilisation

Two sets of criteria are applied for the river channel stabilisation interventions. 1) Hard engineering interventions are available to be applied to channel reaches classified as Very high erosion risk within 3 km of water storages and WTPs. 2) All other channel stabilisation interventions are available to be applied to channel reaches classified as Moderate, High and Very high erosion risk where riparian woody vegetation cover is $\leq 30\%$ based on LiDAR Canopy Height Models or $\leq 40\%$ based on airphoto filtered vegetation cover. Channel reach erosion risk classes are from the ISA project.

5.1.2 Gully stabilisation

Gullies are prioritised based on sediment loads delivered to the stream network, hence their connectivity. To approximate treatment area and perimeter, firstly the Saxton et al. (2012) gullies mapped as polylines had a buffer of 7.5m applied to approximate the width of the features. Second, both the buffered Saxton et al. (2012) gullies and ISA mapped gully polygons had a minimum bounding geometry of Rectangle-Area applied to determine treatment area (ha) and perimeter (km) of application of intervention measures including fencing and revegetation.

Hard engineering interventions are only applied to high risk gullies which are defined as gullies within 3 km of water storage or WTP, and TSS loads of ≥ 100 t/y. The linear gully length is used as the measure for application of engineering works.

5.1.3 Landslide stabilisation

Minimum bounding geometry of Rectangle-Area applied to determine area (ha) or perimeter (km) of application of intervention measures. High risk Landslides – defined as Landslides within 3 km of water storage or WTP, no woody veg cover, and TSS loads of ≥ 100 t/y – include hard engineering options as possible interventions, while remaining landslides without woody vegetation cover had revegetation (woody) and/or fencing intervention extents calculated only.

For all interventions to be considered within a group limit, all measurement units need to be the same, i.e. in hectares. Therefore, fencing extent has been converted to a measure in hectares based on a relationship between Site area and site perimeter [Fence (ha) = $0.216 \cdot \text{Perimeter}^2 + 2.5863 \cdot \text{Perimeter}$].

5.1.4 Point Source controls

Similar interventions as used for Intensive agriculture for pathogen control. Grass filter strips and sediment dams (small, medium and large) were applied to PSS sites where sediments connected to waterways

5.2 Pathogen Intervention Upper Limits

5.2.1 On-Site wastewater Systems

The following rules were followed to generate upper limit values for every single Planning Unit as applied in the model shown in Figure 6. This is Step 6 from section 3.1.5.

Intervention code	Intervention	Criteria
WW_OS_main	Maintenance program	The total number of OSS <100m from watercourse within a PU
WW_OS_rect	Rectify hydraulic failure	The total number of OSS <100m from watercourse within a PU <i>(originally 50% of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU)</i>
WW_OS_upgr	Upgrade systems	The total number of OSS <100m from watercourse within a PU <i>(originally 30% of OSS <50m from watercourse within a PU)</i>
WW_OS_conn	Connection to mains	OSS <50m from watercourse and ≤ 1km from sewer network*

* This is just to see some numbers. Connection to mains requires a certain number (density) of very high to high risk OSS.

Figure 5. Model name: OSS_Step6_Upper_Limits developed by Walter Castillo.

Input data:

- OSS_FINAL
- SEQ_SEWERAGE

- Seqwater_PU_v12

Output data:

- PU_OSS_ULI

Description:

The most up to date OSS layer is used to generate an Upper Limit table with attribute values for each planning unit.

5.2.2 STPs

Currently no interventions provided for STPs.

5.2.3 Stormwater

Detention ponds are allocated to each stormwater outlet with high to very pathogen risk.

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